

RNN aided lidar-based positioning for AMR

Stefano Mutti
 STIIMA-CNR
 Milano, Italy
 stefano.mutti@stiima.cnr.it

Nicola pedrocchi
 STIIMA-CNR
 Milano, Italy
 nicola.pedrocchi@stiima.cnr.it

Abstract—Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMR) are being employed more in nowadays industry, in tasks where a precise positioning algorithm is fundamental for a positive result. AMRs often rely on laser scanner readings in order to perform a precise positioning or docking procedure. Laser scanners output a 1D vector of distances between the sensor center and the surrounding environment. In order to re-position the AMR into a saved position, the AMR has to be moved in a way to match the sensor reading of the saved position with the current one. In this work, an RNN approach is proposed to estimate the registration error between laser scanners and improve the docking precision.

Index Terms—Autonomous mobile robot, recursive neural network, lidar positioning

I. INTRODUCTION

For most of the industrial tasks that involve AMRs, precise positioning is the key factor for a good outcome. In the literature, [1] treats the task as an optimization problem, in which the aim is finding a transformation that minimizes the scans distance, using a segments discretization, while [2] employs angles histograms to associate scans with a map. Classical registration methods have been employed successfully, but struggle to take into consideration multiple sensor readings at once, and for this reason, they are strongly affected by the laser scanner accuracy and precision. To overcome this, we propose a recurrent neural network architecture, in order to leverage multiple readings and have a more robust registration output.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The main problem can be described as an AMR returning to a position that has been "stored", with the most accuracy possible, from a starting position that is nearby the goal position. Storing a position means using a number of laser scanner readings related to a fixed position, and then acting the ARM until the current laser scanner readings match the ones acquired in the saved position. Since the laser is fixed to the ARM, its error is rigidly transported to the robot frame.

Consider an AMR, which position in the environment is described by the vector $\mathbf{p} = [x, y, \theta]$, defining the world-robot transform from the world frame $\{W\}$ to the AMR $\{M\}$ as ${}^M\mathbf{T}_W$, as in eq. 1a, and a laser scanner mounted on-top at frame $\{L\}$ with a known rigid transformation ${}^L\mathbf{T}_M$.

$${}^M\mathbf{T}_W = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) & x \\ -\sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) & y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1a)$$

The laser scanner reads at a certain frequency, and at time t , a fixed-length n vector $\mathcal{D}|t = [d_0, d_1, \dots, d_n]_t$ of distances between the center of the laser and the environment around, where every d_i, d_{i+1} is distanced by a constant β angle. The overall problem aim is minimizing an error function between position $\mathbf{p}|S$ corresponding to a stored reading $S = [l_0, l_1, \dots, l_n]$ and a current one $\mathbf{p}|C$ with $C = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_n]$, by moving the robot appropriately.

Considering two 1D signal from the laser scanner L, S , the positioning error can be defined based on the laser readings as eq. 2, or directly on the final AMR positioning error, which will result in a less noisy value to measure.

$$E(\mathbf{p}|L, \mathbf{p}|C) = \mathbf{p}|L - \mathbf{p}|S \quad (2a)$$

From the AMR point of view, minimizing eq. 2 means moving back the AMR as close as possible to the initial known location. The laser scanner-based error will be used to generate the command velocity for the AMR, and move it back to the initial position. To generate the error, a recursive neural network is used, in which a number k of stored laser reading is fed, joint with a number k of currents sensor reading, and gives as output a three-dimensional error vector.

III. NET ARCHITECTURE AND DATA COLLECTION

The overall net architecture is composed of an initial RNN section, using the GRU mechanism, which outputs feeds 3 parallel fully connected sections, each one outputting a different value of the 3-dimensional error vector, as shown in 1. The RNN input consists of k consecutive readings concatenated of the stored position and the current one. The decision to use an RNN is given by the supposition that consecutive laser readings bear more positioning information than a single one. To gather data for the training, an AMR has been randomly moved in an environment while logging the laser scanner readings. To create the transformation labels between the movements, the AMS has been tracked by an external camera, using a visual tag fixed on the AMR top. In total, the AMR-related data was gathered for 3 hours, for a total of 2500 samples. This data is then augmented, by combining each sample, related to a fixed world position, with a random subset of the other samples, to create a relative displacement as a label and an input vector. This procedure allows us to create a 22500 input-label set that will be used to train, validate and test the net.

Figure 1: net architecture

Figure 2: Error comparison between RNN and ICP approach

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND COMPARISON

The employed architecture dimension consists of 20 hidden-size and 3 layers for the RNN side, with an input of ten consecutive readings (for each stored position and actual reading) with a length of 310. Subsequently, the 3 fully connected parts are equal and consist of 2 layers of 20 and 10 neurons each. To train the network, the PyTorch library has been used [3]. In order to assess the method, the displacement estimation will be done with the newly introduced RNN method, and with a standard iterative closest point algorithm provided by [4]. The AMR used for the experiments is shown in fig 3, with an RPLidar a3 model mounted on top. In the experiments, the AMR is positioned randomly, after a goal position has been stored, and moved back to a stored position, the same for both methods, for a total number of 19 repetitions. The comparison of the final error is shown in fig 2, where the

Figure 3: AMR

absolute value of the final positioning error $[x, y, \theta]$ is shown, and in table I, where the mean error is compared. The final error is measured using the same method used to label the data. It is clearly noticeable that the RNN approach yields a much lower positioning error compared to the ICP one, especially for what concerns the θ angle error.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The method has proved reliable but lacks a generic approach. In future works, will be investigated the usage of transfer learning joined with training on synthetic data. This will shorten the time needed to gather data and aid the network to learn a generic scenario rather than a fixed one.

Table I: Final positioning mean error comparison between ICP and RNN(our) methods

method	x	y	θ
ICP	0.0047	0.0125	0.0103
RNN	0.0037	0.0041	0.0038

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